

Can high angular degree non-radial pulsations be observed in roAp stars?

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Abstract

In the presence of a magnetic field, stellar spectral lines may appear systematically broader in one circular polarisation than in the opposite one. This rotational crossover effect, which is observed in some Ap stars, results from a correlation between the rotational Doppler shift and the different Zeeman shifts of the circularly polarised components.

Crossover of non-rotational origin has been detected in a number of roAp stars as well as in some noAp stars. The most plausible interpretation is that it is induced by the pulsational velocity gradients across the photospheric layer. Pulsational crossover is expected to be detectable even in the case of high angular degree pulsation modes, contrary to luminosity variations. Thus, it may open a new window into unexplored physics in roAp stars.

1 Introduction

Among the main sequence stars of spectral types between late B and early F, 5 to 10% show often extreme over- or under-abundances of a number of chemical elements (e.g., He, Si, Sr, Cr, and the rare earth elements). The abundance anomalies observed at the surface of these Ap stars result from chemical segregation processes that take place within them under the competing effects of various physical mechanisms, including radiative levitation and gravitational settling. The efficiency of these mechanisms is boosted by the stabilising influence of strong magnetic fields on the stellar outer layers.

Indeed, the Ap stars host magnetic fields of kG order that cover their entire surfaces. These fields show a significant degree of large-scale organisation, most often resembling a single dipole whose axis is inclined with respect to the stellar rotation axis. They were acquired by the stars at the time of their formation, are frozen in, and do not show any intrinsic variations. The non-uniform distribution of the chemical elements and of the brightness over the stellar surface is to some extent related with the magnetic field structure. Thus, the Ap stars are *oblique rotators*, which show photometric, spectroscopic and magnetic variations resulting from the changing aspect of their visible hemisphere as the star rotates. The variations of these various observables all occur with the same period, which is the stellar rotation period. The rotation periods of the Ap stars range from ~ 0.5 d to several centuries.

Kurtz (1982) discovered that, in addition, some Ap stars undergo variations with periods of a few minutes. These *rapidly oscillating Ap stars* (roAp stars) are pulsating in high overtone non-radial p modes. The discovery of the roAp stars opened a new field of research, asteroseismology, which has since provided a wealth of new knowledge about the properties of stars and, in particular, the physics of their interiors. Today, 61 roAp stars are known, with pulsation periods ranging from 5 to 25 min and photometric amplitudes up to 0.01 mag (Smalley *et al.*, 2015). Line profile variations caused by pulsation have also been observed (e.g., Kurtz *et al.*, 2006, and references therein).

The detection and characterisation of the pulsations of the roAp stars through photometric and spectroscopic variations are mostly restricted to modes of low angular degree ℓ . Indeed, for $\ell > 2$, the brightness and radial velocity variations caused by non-radial pulsations tend to average out by integration over the visible stellar disk. However, on theoretical grounds, there is no reason to expect the roAp stars to pulsate only in low angular degree modes.

2 The crossover

Babcock (1951) found that, in some spectra of the Ap star HD 125248 (= CS Vir) recorded through a Zeeman analyser, the lines in one of the circular polarisations were systematically broader than in the opposite polarisation. He noted that this effect varied with the period of the photometric, spectroscopic and magnetic variations of the star, and that the line width difference is largest around the phases at which the mean longitudinal magnetic field¹ reverts its sign, or in other words, “crosses over” from negative to positive or vice-versa. Accordingly, he named *crossover* the observed line width difference between the two circular polarisations.

The crossover can be quantitatively characterised by measuring the second-order moment of the spectral line profile recorded in the Stokes parameter V about its centre (Mathys, 1995). The crossover discovered in HD 125248 by Babcock (1951), subsequently observed in other stars by him (Babcock, 1958) and by other authors (e.g., Preston & Pyper, 1965; Preston, 1969; Wolff & Bonsack, 1972), and systematically measured by Mathys (1995), results from the existence of a correlation between the rotational Doppler shift of the contributions to the observed, disk-integrated line coming from different parts of the stellar disk, on the one hand, and the different Zeeman shifts of their right and left circularly polarised components, corresponding to the local magnetic field strength and orientation, on the other hand. This correlation arises from the large scale structure of the field and its inclination with respect to the stellar rotation axis: it is

¹The mean longitudinal magnetic field is the average over the visible stellar hemisphere of the component of the magnetic vector along the line of sight, weighted by the local emergent light intensity.

intrinsic to the oblique rotator model. In what follows, we shall refer to this effect as the *rotational crossover*.

To first order, the rotational crossover is proportional to the projected equatorial velocity of the star, $v \sin i$. It varies in phase quadrature with respect to the mean longitudinal magnetic field, reversing its sign, so that its average value over a rotation cycle is zero.

3 Crossover “anomalies”

Those Ap stars that have a low enough projected equatorial velocity $v \sin i$ and a sufficiently strong magnetic field show lines resolved into their Zeeman split components in high resolution spectra recorded in natural light. In a recent systematic study of the magnetic fields in a statistical sample of such stars, Mathys (2017) detected crossover “anomalies” in several of them:

- The detection at the 99% confidence level of crossover (that is, systematic differences in the spectral line widths between right and left circular polarisation) in HD 965 (whose rotation period exceeds 13 years) and HD 55719 (with a rotation period much longer than 10 years). To account for the observed effect as being rotational crossover would require the radii of these stars to be unrealistically large – much greater than 30 solar radii.
- The occurrence of non-reversing crossover in HD 2453, HD 93507, HD 116114, HD 144897, and possibly also in HD 965, HD 116458 and HD 187474,
- The observation of a crossover varying in phase with the mean longitudinal magnetic field in HD 93507.

The effect observed in the stars listed above cannot be interpreted in terms of rotational crossover. A possible alternative is introduced in the next section.

4 Pulsational crossover

In general, the Stokes V profile of a spectral line emerging at a given point of the stellar surface is antisymmetric about its centre (it has an S-shape). In such a case, for crossover to be observed in a disk-integrated spectrum, some macroscopic velocity field is required, which is non-uniform over the stellar surface, in a way that some large-scale correlation exists between the Doppler shift that it generates and the Zeeman effect across the visible stellar disk. As seen above, the velocity field corresponding to stellar rotation fulfils this requirement. But we already mentioned that the crossover that is observed in some Ap stars cannot be explained by rotation.

The other macroscopic velocity field that is definitely present in some (cool) Ap stars is non-radial pulsation. It has a large-scale structure that makes it a priori suitable for the generation of correlations across the stellar surface between the Doppler shifts resulting from it and the local Zeeman effect. But the crossover that can be produced in that way must mostly average out over a pulsation period, and most integration times required to acquire the spectra of the stars listed at the end of Sect. 3 are significantly longer than the typical pulsation periods of the roAp stars.

In the absence of any suitable macroscopic velocity field, the observation of crossover implies that *locally*, the emergent line profiles in the Stokes V parameter are *not* antisymmetric about their centres. Indeed, this unusual behaviour might potentially occur as the result of one of the following effects (Mathys, 1995):

- The populations of the magnetic substates of the atomic levels involved in the observed transitions depart from LTE.
- The observed lines are formed in a Paschen-Back regime rather than in the linear Zeeman regime. This is definitely not the case.
- There exist velocity gradients along the line of sight in the line-forming region (Landi Degl’Innocenti & Landolfi, 1983).

The first of these effects can certainly be ruled out for the studied lines of the stars of interest. As to the second one, the studied lines are definitely formed in the linear Zeeman regime for the magnetic field strengths of interest. The only plausible explanation is the third one: we do know, indeed, that the pulsation amplitude in roAp stars varies across the depth of the photosphere (e.g., Kurtz *et al.*, 2006).

The departure from antisymmetry of the emergent Stokes V spectral line profile in the presence of velocity gradients along the line of sight is a radiative transfer effect whose calculation is not trivial (Landolfi & Landi Degl’Innocenti, 1996). But as shown in Appendix C of Mathys (2017), one does not need to perform the calculation to show that this effect, integrated over the stellar disk, can generate a non-zero crossover even in a non-rotating star, which does not cancel out over a pulsation period, and varies in phase (or in antiphase) with the mean longitudinal magnetic field. In other words, this *pulsational crossover* can account, at least qualitatively, for all the “anomalous” behaviours reported in Sect. 3.

5 Discussion

One of the most intriguing aspects of the pulsational crossover is its sensitivity to non-radial pulsations of high angular degree ℓ . This results from the fact that the departures from antisymmetry of the local Stokes V line profiles that this effect causes do not average out by integration over the visible stellar disk, contrary to the local brightness fluctuations or the local radial velocity shifts of spectral lines that form the basis of, respectively, the “classical” photometric and spectroscopic methods of detection and study of the pulsations of roAp stars. Thus, exploitation of the pulsational crossover effect opens the door to qualitatively novel studies of Ap star pulsations. On the one hand, observing pulsations of higher degree ℓ in roAp stars in which existing studies were limited to $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ will open unprecedented diagnostic possibilities of the physical processes taking place in these stars. On the other hand, we may become able to detect pulsations in Ap stars that until now appeared to be non-oscillating: for instance, in some stars, the $\ell = 1$ and $\ell = 2$ modes may have pulsation amplitudes below the photometric and/or spectroscopic detection thresholds, while modes of higher angular degree modes may be detectable in spectropolarimetry through the observation of pulsational crossover.

The detections of what is presumably pulsational crossover that were reported by Mathys (2017) are formally significant, but close to the detection threshold. However, they were based on spectropolarimetric observations obtained ~ 20 years ago. New generation spectropolarimeters such as ESPaDOnS (Donati *et al.*, 2006) or HARPSpol (Piskunov *et al.*, 2011) deliver much higher spectral resolution and signal-to-noise ratio. Analysing data obtained with such instruments will enable us to confirm the preliminary detections, to increase considerably the precision of the individual crossover measurements, and to define more

reliably their variation curves. This next step of the project was started recently.

While the pulsational crossover signal does not average out over a pulsation period, its magnitude must be variable with the pulsation frequency. Detecting such variations by acquiring spectropolarimetric observations with a time resolution that is shorter than the stellar pulsation period represents the ultimate test that pulsation is responsible for the new type of crossover found by Mathys (2017). The successful completion of this test will in turn validate the approach that we propose here to detect and study high angular degree non-radial pulsation modes in Ap stars. The observational strategy to be applied is similar to the one that was used to carry out the high time and spectral resolutions that have been used to study pulsation-induced line profile variations in natural light (e.g., Elkin *et al.*, 2008). The splitting of the stellar light into two beams of opposite polarisations and the fact that the polarisation signal in the spectral lines is at most a few percent of the intensity of the unpolarised continuum make the endeavour more challenging and restrict the feasibility of such observations to stars that are sufficiently bright. But meaningful results should be achievable for the brightest roAp stars. We shall further explore this possibility.

To optimise the observational strategy and to extract physical information from the crossover measurements, an appropriate theoretical basis is required. For this purpose, we have undertaken the computation of numerical simulations of the effect of the pulsational crossover on the Stokes V line profiles. We use a model Ap star pulsating in a non-radial mode aligned with the magnetic axis and solve the equation of transfer of polarised radiation at a grid of points over the stellar surface, taking into account the pulsation-induced gradient of radial velocity in the photosphere. Then we integrate over the visible stellar disk the emergent Stokes profiles, repeating this process at a number of phases along the rotation period. With this numerical simulation code, we shall be able to set detection limits for the pulsational crossover and to understand the diagnostic potential of its observation, in particular with respect to the high angular degree pulsation modes and to the stellar physics to which they give access. Moreover, we plan to perform inversions of the spatially averaged synthetic spectra to evaluate our ability to recover the information of the input pulsation velocities and magnetic field. Success in this undertaking holds the promise of opening a new window into unexplored physics in roAp stars.

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